

FROM REACTIVE TO PROACTIVE MANAGEMENT: THE ROLE OF THE WATERWAY MONITORING PLAN (WMP) ON BRAZILIAN RIVERS

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ABSTRACT

Brazil's vast territory includes over 40,000 km of economically navigable rivers, which are strategic for transporting cargo like grains and minerals. However, navigability is challenged by a highly variable hydrological regime, creating seasonal "critical passages" that require agile and well-planned maintenance, such as dredging. The National Department of Transport Infrastructure (DNIT) traditionally faced delays in contracting these interventions due to planning complexities. To address this, the Waterway Monitoring Plan (WMP) was established in 2020. The program provides essential data—such as water levels, bathymetry, and flow rates—for hydrological modeling and predictive analysis, forming the basis for data-driven management. The WMP's effectiveness was proven during the 2023-2024 cycle, marked by extreme climatic events. In the severe droughts in the Amazon and Paraguai River basins, continuous monitoring was crucial for planning emergency dredging. Conversely, in Southern Brazil, which suffered from historical floods, the absence of a WMP hindered the emergency response. This demonstrates that the WMP is a fundamental tool for Brazilian waterway management. Its continued implementation and expansion will strengthen the resilience and efficiency of Brazil's transport infrastructure in the face of climate change.

Keywords: *Waterway planning; large-scale bathymetry, large tropical rivers, climate change, navigability maintenance.*

1 INTRODUÇÃO

Inland navigation plays a strategic role in Brazil's multimodal logistics system. With a land area of over 8.5 million square kilometers and 12 major hydrographic regions, the country has vast potential for waterway transport. It is estimated that about 40,000 kilometers of Brazilian rivers are economically navigable, although the country uses only half of this potential (ANTAQ, 2023). The Brazilian Government, aware of the importance of sustainable transport policies, promotes actions to encourage the use of this modal. In 2023, about 128.5 million tons of cargo were transported on inland waterways, including grains, ores, and other products (ANTAQ, 2025).

Despite the natural navigability of many rivers, the Brazilian hydrological regime is highly variable. Seasonal differences in water levels can be significant, creating stretches with reduced depth that hinder or prevent safe navigation. These stretches, known as "critical passages," require maintenance interventions, such as dredging, which demand technical planning and agility.

The National Department of Transport Infrastructure (DNIT) is the federal agency responsible for the maintenance and operation of the waterway infrastructure (DNIT, 2020) and faces the challenge of planning these interventions in a complex scenario. Traditional approaches often result in delays in contracting works, which impacts navigability, increases logistics costs, and reduces the reliability of river transport.

In response to this scenario, DNIT structured the Waterway Monitoring Plan (WMP) in 2020. The program aims to generate updated and continuous technical data to support the planning and execution of interventions on Brazil's main waterways. Through the monitoring of variables such as water level, flow, sedimentation, and bathymetry, the plan contributes to modeling river behavior and to the predictability of critical navigation scenarios (DNIT, 2022).

This article aims to present the structure, objectives, and strategic importance of the WMP for the maintenance of Brazil's inland waterways. The analysis emphasizes its role during the 2023–2024 cycle, marked by extreme climatic events in the Amazon, Paraguay, and the river basins of the South region. The WMP has proven to be fundamental for decision-making, for navigation safety, and for strengthening the resilience of the transport infrastructure in the face of climate change.

2 HYDROLOGICAL CONTEXT AND NAVIGATIONAL CHALLENGES

Five of the world's ten largest rivers are in Brazil, including the Amazonas River, three of its tributaries (Madeira, Negro, and Japurá), and the Paraná River (Latrubesse et al., 2005). Therefore, given this hydrological scale, significant hydrological variability in Brazilian rivers is natural. Due to the different climatic and geographical dynamics acting on the major hydrographic regions, the rivers exhibit significant level variations

throughout the year (Figure 1). These variations directly affect navigability, especially during drought periods, when several stretches become shallow or present obstacles to the safe passage of vessels.

Historical Time Series of Mean Water Level for Brazilian Rivers

Figure 1: Historical series of mean water levels for five Brazilian rivers (1990–2024). The solid blue line shows the mean water level, while the dotted lines indicate the historical maximum (red) and minimum (orange) values for the period. The shaded area highlights the 2023–2024 extreme events period.

Although many waterways are naturally navigable for most of the year, there are stretches where seasonal restrictions known as "critical passages" occur. At these points, the available depth may be insufficient for commercial vessels, posing a risk to navigation safety and increasing travel time and operational costs. In more severe situations, these stretches can become impassable, interrupting essential logistical routes for cargo transport.

In addition to natural seasonality, the occurrence of extreme events—such as prolonged droughts or intense floods—has become more frequent and impactful in recent years, possibly associated with global climate change. These events abruptly alter the hydrological behavior of rivers, further complicating the planning and execution of interventions like dredging or emergency buoyage.

The challenge faced by DNIT is to ensure the maintenance of navigability throughout the year, even in the face of these variable and often unpredictable conditions. This requires detailed and up-to-date knowledge of the rivers' conditions, including the dynamics of the riverbed, flows, and sedimentation. Furthermore, the contracting process for interventions like dredging involves legal and administrative steps that can take weeks or months—a timeframe incompatible with the urgency that critical situations often demand.

In this context, the importance of continuous monitoring systems and planning based on reliable data becomes evident. The ability to anticipate hydrological behaviors, identify critical points, and simulate risk scenarios is essential for the efficient management of the national waterway infrastructure. The absence of these elements tends to result in reactive interventions, with higher costs, lower effectiveness, and increased risk for navigation operators.

3 THE WATERWAY MONITORING PLAN (WMP)

To improve the planning and execution of waterway maintenance, the National Department of Transport Infrastructure (DNIT) structured the Waterway Monitoring Plan (WMP) in 2020. The plan is part of the Waterway Maintenance Program (PMA), and its mission is to maintain the navigable waterways in ideal conditions for navigability and safety, ensuring the predictability of water levels throughout the year (Seefeldler et al., 2024).

3.1. Objectives and Data Collection Methodology

The central objective of the WMP is to generate systematic and continuous knowledge about the physical characteristics of the rivers, with a focus on navigability. This knowledge is acquired through the regular execution of a set of hydrographic and hydrosedimentological surveys, detailed in Table 1. The activities range from single-beam and multibeam bathymetry for riverbed modeling to flow measurement with ADCP and the monitoring of fluviometric stations for near-real-time water level data.

Table 1 – Activities carried out in the WMP

ACTIVITY	OBJECTIVE	PRODUCTS GENERATED
Single-beam Bathymetry	Obtain the general morphology of the riverbed (from bank to bank and/or Navigation Channel)	DTM – Digital Terrain Model and DEM – Digital Elevation Model, point clouds with orthometric elevations and isobath lines
Multibeam Bathymetry	Obtain a detailed model of the bottom in critical navigation areas.	DTM – Digital Terrain Model and DEM – Digital Elevation Model, point clouds with orthometric elevations and isobath lines
Hydrometric Measurements with ADCP	Measure flow, velocity, and direction of river currents	Hydrodynamic profiles, flow rates by section and key curve
Suspended Sediment	Evaluate composition of the bed and suspended load	Granulometric data and sediment concentration
Level Reference (LR)	Ensure altimetric precision of GNSS collections	Geodetic base for level corrections
Fluviometric Stations	Monitor variation of water level with high temporal resolution with collection every 15 minutes and variations over time.	Time series of water level

Geomorphological and Hydrosedimentological Characterization	Integrate physical data of the river to understand its dynamics and evolution	Hydraulic Model
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Source: Technical Archive of DAQ/DNIT

3.2. From Data Collection to Intelligence: Modeling for Decision Support

The continuous collection of data is the foundation for transforming information into intelligence for management. In this vision, the generated products (Table 1) are essential inputs that are feeding computational models currently in development, whose objective is to create a virtual representation of the navigable stretches.

With these models, it is possible to perform hydrodynamic and sediment transport simulations under different scenarios. This predictive capability is the cornerstone for data-driven decision-making, which translates into direct benefits for planning maintenance interventions (DNIT, 2022):

- **Proactive Identification:** It allows for identifying "critical passages" with greater precision and in advance, which could compromise navigation during subsequent low-water seasons.
- **Channel Optimization:** It assists in locating and defining the ideal navigation channel geometry (alignment, width, and depth), contributing to safer and more efficient passage.
- **Strategic Dredging Planning:** It guides the selection of the best period for dredging critical points, taking into account fluvial dynamics and sediment transport to maximize the longevity of the intervention.

Additionally, data from telemetering stations integrated into the HidroWEB system (ANA, 2025) provide situational awareness of the monitored rivers in near-real-time.

3.3. Implementation Status and Strategic Partnerships

Currently, the WMP is implemented on the main waterways of the North and Central-West regions, such as the Madeira, Tapajós, Tocantins, and Paraguai rivers (Figure 2). The expansion to other basins, such as those in the South region, is in the planning phase, driven by the lessons learned from the climatic events of the 2023-2024 cycle.

To consolidate the program, DNIT has established strategic institutional partnerships, notably the agreements with the USACE (U.S. Army Corps of Engineers) and the Geological Survey of Brazil (SGB/CPRM), in addition to the various contracts for its execution, which together add technical knowledge and methodological support.

Figure 2: Implementation status of the Waterway Monitoring Plan (WMP) across Brazil. The legend indicates programs under execution (red), in planning (green), and preliminary Hydrographic Surveys (blue). The colored polygons delineate the 12 major Brazilian hydrographic regions.

The WMP redefines waterway management in Brazil by introducing a preventive methodology, based on scientific and technological data, with the purpose of optimizing operational efficiency, raising navigation safety standards, and increasing the predictability of the modal. The implementation of the plan, therefore, constitutes a substantial advancement in the characterization and systematic monitoring of navigable rivers and the national waterway infrastructure.

4 EXTREME CLIMATIC EVENTS IN THE 2023-2024 HYDROLOGICAL CYCLE

The 2023-2024 hydrological cycle was marked by climatic extremes with a major impact on the navigability of Brazilian rivers. While the Amazon and Paraguay basins faced severe droughts, the South region of Brazil was hit by intense rains that resulted in historical floods. These contrasting events highlighted the vulnerability of waterways to climatic variations and reinforced the need for structured monitoring and response systems.

In the Amazon basin, the droughts recorded in the 2023-2024 cycles was the most intense of the century. On October 27, 2023, the water level of the Negro River at the port of Manaus reached a minimum level of 12.70 m, the lowest record since the beginning of the historical series in 1902. This record was broken on October 4, 2024, when the level reached 12.66 m. Levels below 14 m at this location are classified as "extreme drought," and in 2024, 62 municipalities in the state of Amazonas declared a state of emergency (Andrade and Queiroz, 2024). The impact was widespread: the Madeira River showed exceptionally low levels, affecting critical stretches between Porto Velho and Itacoatiara, while the Tapajós River suffered a drastic reduction in draft, compromising grain transport. As illustrated in Figure 1 (charts 1, 2, and 3), the minimum levels in 2023 and 2024 were the lowest since 1990. The Óbidos station is the most downstream station on the Amazonas River without tidal influences, and the minimum levels at this station show evidence of the widespread impact of the drought throughout the Amazon region in its various sub-basins.

The effectiveness of the Waterway Monitoring Plan (WMP) was exemplified on the Madeira River, where prior knowledge of the riverbed allowed for a swift and assertive declaration of a state of emergency. In contrast, the Amazonas River, due to its history of navigability that did not require recurrent dredging, did not have a WMP implemented. The severe drought of 2023 exposed the vulnerability of this approach: the absence of robust data resulted in planning difficulties and uncertainties in estimating volumes for dredging. Consequently,

the emergency contracting process extended for months, a timeframe that, with the support of the WMP, could have been reduced to weeks.

The situation was analogous in the Paraguai River basin, which is also covered by the WMP. The river levels reached historical minimums, leading to the declaration of an emergency. At the Ladário station, the level reached -0.67 m, the lowest index since 1900 (Climainfo, 2024). At Porto Esperança, the minimum level since 1990 occurred on October 27, 2024 (-1.98 m), with the lowest monthly average also recorded in October 2024 (-1.75 m), as shown in the fourth chart of figure 1. However, different from an isolated event, the Paraguai River basin has been facing a prolonged drought since 2019, without seasonal recovery of its normal levels. The analysis by Santos and Slater (2025) suggests that this scenario may persist, indicating that the probability of the river remaining at low levels after a year of drought is high, a pattern consistent with long drought cycles observed in the past. These consecutive droughts occurring in the Paraguai River basin compromise the waterway that connects Brazil to Paraguay and Argentina, affecting the export of ore and agricultural products. The severity of the droughts led to the declaration of an emergency in several municipalities and required swift emergency dredging actions to ensure minimal navigability on the Paraguai River Waterway.

In the cases of the Madeira, Tapajós, and Paraguai rivers, the WMP played a fundamental role. The updated data on bathymetry, flow, and water levels provided the technical basis for the emergency declarations and allowed DNIT to identify the most critical stretches, optimizing dredging planning and anticipating necessary actions.

In stark contrast, the South region of Brazil was impacted by torrential rains. In May 2024, the average precipitation in Rio Grande do Sul was 4.5 times higher than the historical monthly average, making it the rainiest month since 1910 (Marengo et al., 2024). The floods affected navigable rivers such as the Jacuí and Taquari. The São Jerônimo station, located downstream from their confluence, recorded its maximum level on November 20, 2023, with 9.07 m. In Figure 1, which represents the daily average levels for each month, the highest record was in September 2023 with 5.53 m. In that region, the absence of an implemented WMP hindered the systematic collection of data and the planning of emergency responses. The interruption of measurements at the station between May and September 2024, visible in figure 1, coincides with the peak of the historical flood and highlights the severity of the event.

The simultaneous occurrence of extreme droughts and floods in different regions of the country reinforces the importance of expanding the WMP as a national policy for continuous monitoring. By providing robust and timely data, the plan proves essential for increasing the resilience of the waterway transport system in the face of climate change.

5 RESULTS AND BENEFITS OF THE WMP FOR WATERWAY MANAGEMENT

Since its implementation in 2020, the Waterway Monitoring Plan (WMP) has established itself as a strategic tool for the efficient management of Brazil's inland waterways. The systematic and continuous collection of hydrographic and hydrosedimentological data has enabled significant advances on several fronts, from intervention planning to emergency response.

The main results achieved with the WMP include:

- **Reduced Emergency Response Time:** The availability of updated WMP data was crucial for the agile response to the severe droughts of 2023-2024 on the Madeira, Tapajós, and Paraguai rivers. It provided the technical basis for declaring a state of emergency and allowed for dredging contracts to be executed with greater speed and precision, a stark contrast to the delays faced on the unmonitored Amazonas River.
- **Improved Dredging Planning:** Detailed knowledge of critical shoaling points, based on updated bathymetry and sediment analysis, has enabled the prioritization of stretches with the greatest impact on navigability. This data-driven approach not only increases operational efficiency but also optimizes resource allocation, potentially reducing costs.
- **Development of Predictive Models:** The database generated by the WMP is being used to build hydrodynamic and sedimentological models in the HEC-RAS 2D, the River Analysis System software for hydraulic models. These models can simulate river behavior under different climatic and operational scenarios, which is fundamental for medium and long-term maintenance planning and aligns waterway management with the "Smart Rivers" concept.
- **Strengthening of a Data-Driven Management Culture:** The existence of an institutional routine for collecting, processing, and analyzing waterway data reinforces the adoption of technical criteria in decisions. This fosters greater transparency, predictability, and safety for the navigation sector.

These results demonstrate that the WMP transcends simple data generation: it transforms how Brazil plans and executes the maintenance of its waterways, promoting a **proactive and evidence-based management style**. By anticipating risks, identifying trends, and supporting strategic decisions, the WMP establishes itself as an essential instrument for strengthening national river transport.

5.1. Future Perspectives

The future development of the WMP is focused on expanding its impact and technological capabilities. The main upcoming steps for DNIT include:

- **Data Consolidation:** Consolidating all data generated by the WMP into a single, standardized institutional Spatial Database. This will allow for integration with geoinformation platforms and real-time dashboards, improving situational awareness for decision-makers and users.
- **Program Expansion:** Expanding the WMP to new regions, with a strategic focus on the waterways of Southern Brazil. This has become a priority after the contrasting emergency response during the 2024 floods, aiming to ensure the entire national territory is covered by a modern monitoring policy.

6 FINAL CONSIDERATIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

The Waterway Monitoring Plan (WMP) represents an evolution in how Brazil plans and executes the maintenance of its inland waterways. In a country of continental dimensions with an extensive and diverse hydrographic network, dealing with hydrological variability and the impacts of extreme events requires more than just reactive responses: it demands intelligence, foresight, and a solid technical foundation.

The experience gained from implementing the WMP on the main waterways of the North and Central-West regions has demonstrated in practice the benefits of continuous monitoring, with updated data and the integration of different environmental variables. The results achieved to date—such as greater precision in dredging, agility in emergency situations, and the development of predictive models—reinforce the WMP's potential as a foundational instrument for national waterway management.

The 2023-2024 cycle, marked by severe droughts and historical floods, clearly highlighted the challenges the country faces with climate change and the intensification of extreme events. The absence of the WMP in certain regions, such as Southern Brazil, limited the technical response capacity and reinforced the need for its expansion across the entire national territory.

In this regard, future perspectives for the WMP include:

- The expansion of the program to new hydrographic regions, with an emphasis on the South region;
- The consolidation of all data generated by the WMP in a standardized and systematic manner into an institutional Spatial Database;
- The strengthening of partnerships with research institutions and international bodies, such as National Water and Basic Sanitation Agency (ANA), Geological Survey of Brazil (SGB), Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE), National Waterway Transportation Agency (ANTAQ) and U.S. Army Corps of Engineers (USACE);
- The use of emerging technologies, such as remote sensing by satellites and artificial intelligence, to enhance data collection and analysis.

Consolidating the WMP as a national public policy is essential to ensure the resilience and efficiency of Brazil's waterway infrastructure. Waterway transport is strategic for the country's economic and sustainable development—and the knowledge generated by the WMP is the foundation for ensuring its continuity in the face of future hydrological and climate uncertainties.

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